

A New Proof on the Growth Factor in Gaussian Elimination for Generalized Higham Matrices

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Abstract : The generalized Higham matrix is a complex symmetric matrix $A=B+iC$, where both B and C are Hermitian positive definite, and i is the imaginary unit. The growth factor in Gaussian elimination is less than $\sqrt{2}$ for this kind of matrices. In this paper, we give a new brief proof on this result by different techniques, which can be understood very easily, and obtain some new findings.

Keywords : CSPD matrix, positive definite, Schur complement, Higham matrix, Gaussian elimination, Growth factor

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